

Environmental Sustainability in Europe

The Russian-Ukrainian conflict could generate a countertrend in the upward convergence of the environmental sustainability index in European countries

The European Innovation Scoreboard-EIS calculates the value of environmental sustainability. Environmental sustainability is considered as the impact of three different indicators, namely: resource productivity, exposure to air pollution from fine particles, development of technologies related to the environment.

Keywords: Environmental Economics, Valuation of Environmental Effects, Sustainability, Government Policy, Ecological Economics.

JEL Classification: Q5, Q51, Q56, Q58, Q57

Ranking of European countries by value of environmental sustainability in 2021. Malta is in first place by value of environmental sustainability with a value of 156.28, followed by Denmark with an amount equal to 136.06 units and by Switzerland with a value of 130.46 units. In the middle of the table there are Bulgaria with a value of 91.09 units, followed by Slovenia with a value of 86.03 units and Greece with a value of 84.24 units. Bosnia and Herzegovina closed the ranking with an environmental sustainability value of 28.99, followed by Latvia with an amount of 23.19 and Montenegro with a value of 0.00. On average in 2021 the value of environmental sustainability in European countries was equal to an amount of 83.80 units.

Ranking of European countries by percentage change in the value of environmental sustainability between 2014 and 2021. North Macedonia ranks first in terms of the percentage change in environmental sustainability with an amount equal to 272.60% equal to a value of 24,74 units. Turkey is in second place with a percentage change value equal to an amount of 80.57% equal to a value of 23.08 units. Malta with a percentage change value equal to an amount of 58.93% equal to an amount of 57.94 units. In the middle of the table there are France with a variation equal to an amount of 5.43% equal to an amount of 6.16 units, followed by the Netherlands with a value equal to 4.15% equal to an amount of 5.18 units and Germany with a value of 4.14% equal to an amount of 4.90 units. Israel closes the ranking with a value equal to -44.42% or equivalent to -27.33 units, followed by Ukraine with a value of -62.87% equal to a value of 78.34 units, and Bosnia with a value equal to 68.35% equal to an amount of 62.62 units. Overall, between 2014 and 2021 the value of the average value of environmental sustainability decreased from an amount of 84.17 to a value of 83.80 units or equal to a variation of -0.38 units equal to a value of -0.44%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering with the k-Means algorithm was carried out below. The Silhouette coefficient was used to identify the optimal number of clusters. The optimal number of clusters associated with the highest value of the Silhouette coefficient is equal to 2 as indicated below, that is:

- *Cluster 1:* Portugal, Turkey, Latvia, Iceland, Israel, North Macedonia, Serbia, Estonia, Cyprus, Romania, Poland, Montenegro;

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Researcher at LUM Enterprise S.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Italy, European Union. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

- *Cluster 2:* Austria, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Spain, Belgium, Italy, Slovakia, Norway, Netherlands, Lithuania, Switzerland, Denmark, Czech Republic, Ireland, Malta, Sweden, Finland, Hungary, Greece, United Kingdom, Ukraine, Croatia, Bulgaria, Bosnia, Slovenia.

Considering the two clusters and calculating the value of the median, it results that the value of the median of cluster 1-C1 is equal to 38.71 while the value of the median of cluster 2-C2 is equal to 108.8. It therefore follows that the countries of cluster 2 have an environmental sustainability value equal to 2.81 times the environmental sustainability value of the countries of cluster 1. The ordering of clusters is: $C2 > C1$. Looking at the map of clustered countries by level of environmental sustainability, it appears that substantially almost all European countries have high levels of respect for the environment while countries that have low levels are marginal and do not constitute a geographical grouping. It therefore follows that the choice to follow or not a production trend oriented towards environmental sustainability does not depend on geographical factors but rather on institutional, governmental, regulatory, and cultural factors in a broad sense.

Network Analysis. A network analysis was carried out below to verify if there are strong links between European countries in terms of environmental sustainability. The Manhattan distance was used to carry out the network analysis. The general characteristics of the dataset are indicated below:

- Number of nodes equal to 38;
- Number of edges equal to 76;
- Average degree equal to 4;
- Density equal to 0.108.

Based on the analysis carried out, the following links are found between the countries, namely:

- The Netherlands has a link with Denmark with a coefficient of 0.57 and with Switzerland equal with a value of 0.5;
- Denmark has a link with the Netherlands equal to 0.57 and with Switzerland equal to 0.35;
- Switzerland has a link with the Netherlands with a coefficient of 0.5 and a link with Denmark of 0.35;
- Estonia and Israel are linked in a connection with a coefficient value of 0.64;
- Greece is connected with Hungary with an amount equal to 0.57;
- Hungary is connected with Greece with a value of 0.57, with the United Kingdom with an amount equal to 0.67, with Finland with an amount equal to 0.59;
- Croatia is connected with the United Kingdom with a value of 0.55;
- United Kingdom is connected with Croatia with a value of 0.55, with Hungary with an amount of 0.67, with Finland with an amount of 0.52;
- Finland is connected with Hungary with an amount equal to 0.59, with the United Kingdom with an amount equal to 0.52 units, and with Sweden with a value equal to 0.79;
- Sweden is connected with Finland with an amount of 0.79, with Ireland with an amount of 0.73 and with the Czech Republic with a value of 0.58;
- Ireland is connected with Sweden with an amount equal to 0.73, and with the Czech Republic with an amount equal to 0.72;
- The Czech Republic relates to Sweden with a value equal to 0.58 and with Ireland with an amount equal to 0.72 units.
- Germany is connected with France with an amount equal to 0.4, with Luxembourg with a value equal to 0.6, with Spain with a value equal to 0.68 and with Italy with an amount equal to 0.74;
- France is connected to Germany with an amount of 0.4, with Spain with an amount of 0.64;

- Spain is connected with France with an amount of 0.64, with Germany with an amount of 0.68, with Italy with a value of 0.29;
- Italy relates to Germany with a value of 0.74 and with Spain with a value of 0.29.

Therefore, there are significant links between European countries that show a convergent trend with respect to environmental sustainability.

Conclusions. The issue of environmental sustainability is increasingly relevant within the context of the economic policies of the European Union. However, it should be considered that between 2014 and 2021 the average value of the environmental sustainability indicator decreased in Europe by 0.44%. In any case, most European countries converge on environmental sustainability. There are some countries that show very close links in adopting environmental sustainability policies. Although the data scenario turns out to be positive, it is necessary to consider that the Russian-Ukrainian conflict could have a very negative impact in terms of environmental sustainability. In fact, many European countries, to cope with rising gas and energy prices, have decided to delay the shutdown of nuclear power plants and to return to using coal power plants. Therefore, it is likely that in the next 18-36 months there will be a significant worsening of the environmental sustainability index in Europe.

References

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Ranking dei paesi per variazione percentuale della sostenibilit ambientale tra il 2014 ed il 2021

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	North Macedonia	24,74	272,62	20	Denmark	3,93	2,97
2	Turkey	23,08	80,57	21	Switzerland	2,77	2,17
3	Malta	57,94	58,93	22	Luxembourg	0,19	0,16
4	Poland	15,43	31,27	23	Austria	-0,05	-0,05
5	Slovenia	19,88	30,05	24	Croatia	-0,04	-0,05
6	Belgium	25,37	25,89	25	Lithuania	-4,73	-4,16
7	Italy	26,27	25,38	26	Finland	-7,14	-7,96
8	Iceland	12,73	21,83	27	Norway	-13,41	-10,25
9	Latvia	4,15	21,81	28	United Kingdom	-9,31	-10,34
10	Bulgaria	14,23	18,52	29	Greece	-11,46	-11,97
11	Spain	13,15	12,43	30	Portugal	-8,41	-17,21
12	Estonia	7,56	12,33	31	Hungary	-21,52	-22,26
13	Ireland	9,42	10,27	32	Romania	-21,63	-35,21
14	Slovakia	7,41	6,89	33	Cyprus	-17,61	-36,72
15	Czechia	6,35	6,79	34	Serbia	-27,11	-41,88
16	Sweden	5,57	6,26	35	Israel	-27,33	-44,42
17	France	6,16	5,43	36	Ukraine	-78,34	-62,87
18	Netherlands	5,18	4,15	37	Bosnia and Herzegovina	-62,62	-68,35
19	Germany	4,90	4,14				

	2021	Feature 1	Cluster	Silhouette
6	30.3376	Cyprus	C1	0.655902
10	68.825	Estonia	C1	0.661978
18	34.1985	Israel	C1	0.668449
19	71.0287	Iceland	C1	0.675191
23	23.1858	Latvia	C1	0.675516
24	0	Montenegro	C1	0.610468
25	33.8155	North Macedonia	C1	0.665051
29	64.7719	Poland	C1	0.63456
30	40.453	Portugal	C1	0.684133
31	39.8042	Romania	C1	0.641901
32	37.628	Serbia	C1	0.664311
36	51.7289	Turkey	C1	0.682559
1	108.803	Austria	C2	0.693543
2	28.9925	Bosnia and Her...	C2	0.569224
3	123.357	Belgium	C2	0.688414
4	91.0877	Bulgaria	C2	0.548546
5	130.461	Switzerland	C2	0.681979
7	99.8552	Czechia	C2	0.675119
8	123.434	Germany	C2	0.6931
9	136.03	Denmark	C2	0.680395
11	84.2444	Greece	C2	0.630362
12	118.978	Spain	C2	0.689521
13	82.5581	Finland	C2	0.641657
14	119.613	France	C2	0.693412
15	78.4098	Croatia	C2	0.58416
16	75.1715	Hungary	C2	0.640944
17	101.115	Ireland	C2	0.67542
20	129.759	Italy	C2	0.688069
21	108.902	Lithuania	C2	0.680357
22	121.754	Luxembourg	C2	0.691747
26	156.277	Malta	C2	0.669454
27	129.917	Netherlands	C2	0.685833
28	117.333	Norway	C2	0.686654
33	94.5004	Sweden	C2	0.65983
34	86.0285	Slovenia	C2	0.520768
35	114.927	Slovakia	C2	0.685374
37	46.2747	Ukraine	C2	0.605319
38	80.7123	United Kingdom	C2	0.614019

Ranking dei paesi per sostenibilità ambientale

Rank	Countries	2021	Rank	Countries	2021
1	Malta	156,28	20	Greece	84,24
2	Denmark	136,03	21	Finland	82,56
3	Switzerland	130,46	22	United Kingdom	80,71
4	Netherlands	129,92	23	Croatia	78,41
5	Italy	129,76	24	Hungary	75,17
6	Germany	123,43	25	Iceland	71,03
7	Belgium	123,36	26	Estonia	68,83
8	Luxembourg	121,75	27	Poland	64,77
9	France	119,61	28	Turkey	51,73
10	Spain	118,98	29	Ukraine	46,27
11	Norway	117,33	30	Portugal	40,45
12	Slovakia	114,93	31	Romania	39,80
13	Lithuania	108,90	32	Serbia	37,63
14	Austria	108,80	33	Israel	34,20
15	Ireland	101,11	34	North Macedonia	33,82
16	Czechia	99,86	35	Cyprus	30,34
17	Sweden	94,50	36	Bosnia and Herzegovina	28,99
18	Bulgaria	91,09	37	Latvia	23,19
19	Slovenia	86,03	38	Montenegro	0,00